

SOME BASES OF PHYSIOLOGICAL INTEREST.

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At one time, it seemed probable that chaksine iodide, an alkaloid isolated from *Cassia absus* by Siddiqui and Ahmed (*Proc. Indian Acad. Sci.*, 1935, 3, 421) had the structure represented by (I). It was thought of interest to synthesise the substance.

It was expected that β -hydroxy- β -phenylethyldimethylguanidine would add methyl iodide to give (I). Schotte, Priewe and Roescheisen (*Z. physiol. Chem.*, 1928, 174, 119) have prepared phenyldiethylguanidine by condensing diethyl cyanamide and aniline hydrochloride in a sealed tube for 20 hours. But dimethyl cyanamide did not give the corresponding guanidine with β -hydroxyphenylethylamine* although no difficulty was experienced in condensing it with aniline at ordinary pressure. Phenyldimethylguanidine readily gave a quaternary iodide with methyl iodide.

By the interaction of β -hydroxy- β -phenylethylamine and methyl- ψ -thiourea hydroiodide, the hydroiodide of guanidine (II) was readily obtained in good yield. But the conversion of (II) into (I) has not yet succeeded.

As it became apparent that the structure of chaksine is perhaps more complicated than was supposed at first, this line of investigation was not further stressed at this stage. In the present paper a description is included of some amines of physiological interest.

β -Hydroxy- β -phenylethylmethylamine has been prepared in good yield by the hydrolysis of the methyl iodide addition product of the Schiff's base of β -hydroxy- β -phenylethylamine and piperonal. Similarly, β -hydroxy- β -3:4-methylenedioxyphenylethylmethylamine (methylenedioxyadrenaline, III) has been prepared in an analogous way. This latter substance has been prepared by Barger and Jowett (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1905, 87, 970) from 3:4-methylenedioxyphenylethylene and the properties of this substance agree

* This experiment was done under ordinary conditions. It is intended to carry out the reaction under pressure.

with those obtained in the present investigation. β -Hydroxy- β -phenylethyl trimethylammonium iodide (IV, β -phenyletholine iodide) and the corresponding 3':4'-methylenedioxy derivative have also been synthesised.

(IV)

E X P E R I M E N T A L .

Phenyldimethylguanidine.—A mixture of dimethyl cyanamide (0.5 g.) and aniline hydrochloride (1 g.) was heated at 110–120° for 2 hours. The product was dissolved in water and extracted with ether. The aqueous layer was basified and then extracted with ether. After removal of the solvent, the syrup crystallised *in vacuo* after two days. It was recrystallised from petrol ether and ether in colourless needles, m.p. 90°. (Found: N, 25.2. $\text{C}_9\text{H}_{13}\text{N}_3$ requires N, 25.7 per cent). The substance combines with atmospheric carbon dioxide readily and is difficult to obtain analytically pure.

Phenyldimethylguanidinium Iodide, m.p. 188° (decomp.) after crystallisation from acetone and ether, was obtained when a mixture of the foregoing guanidine (0.4 g.) and methyl iodide (2 c.c.) in dry benzene (5 c.c.) was left overnight. (Found: N, 13.5. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_3\text{I}$ requires N, 13.7 per cent).

β -Hydroxyphenylethylamine could not be prepared very satisfactorily by the method of Wolfheim (*Ber.*, 1914, 47, 1444). But the following modification worked better :

Benzaldehyde cyanhydrin (16 g.) dissolved in 30% alcohol (250 c.c.) was cooled to -10° and reduced with 500 g. of sodium amalgam (4%). The solution was kept neutral as far as possible by the addition of requisite quantities of 50% acetic acid from time to time. The addition of the amalgam was so regulated that the addition of the whole quantity required about 5 hours. The reaction was carried in a stout stoppered bottle. The temperature of the solution was never allowed to rise above -5° . The solution was then filtered from a green flocculent impurity and the clear filtrate acidified with hydrochloric acid and evaporated down to 50 c.c. and extracted repeatedly with ether (100 c.c.). The acidic aqueous portion was basified with 40% sodium hydroxide solution. During neutralisation the temperature should not rise above 10° . The base was extracted with ether (150 c.c.), the ethereal solution dried over

potassium carbonate and slightly moist carbon dioxide passed into the ethereal solution, when the carbonate of the base was precipitated, m.p. 111-13°, yield 4.5 g. The dried carbonate (1 g.) was suspended in dry ether and treated with an ethereal solution of hydrogen chloride. After removal of ether in *vacuo*, the hydrochloride of β -hydroxyphenylethylamine (0.8 g.) crystallised from a mixture of ether and alcohol, m.p. 195°. (Found: N, 7.68. $C_8H_{12}ON$, HCl requires N, 8.0 per cent).

A solution of β -hydroxyphenylethylamine carbonate (0.2 g.) in hot alcohol was treated with picronic acid (0.4 g.) dissolved in alcohol and cooled. The *picronolate*, m.p. 198° (decomp.) crystallised in fine yellow needles from alcohol. (Found: N, 17.44. $C_{18}H_{19}O_4N_3$ requires N, 17.45 per cent). The *oxalate*, m.p. 171-72°, crystallised in thin leaflets from alcohol. [Found: N, 7.60. $(C_8H_{11}NO)_2 \cdot C_2H_2O_4$, requires N, 7.69 per cent].

The *monobenzoyl* derivative of β -hydroxyphenylethylamine is formed by benzoylating β -hydroxyphenylethylamine carbonate with excess of benzoyl chloride and sodium hydroxide solution. It crystallised from alcohol in fine needles, m.p. 146-47°. (Found: N, 6.14. $C_{15}H_{15}O_2N$ requires N, 5.8 per cent). We are able to confirm the statement (*cf. Ber.*, 1914, 47, 1445) that it is a *N*-benzoyl derivative. *N*-*O*-dibenzoyl- β -hydroxyphenylethylamine can be prepared in pyridine solution by the usual method. It crystallises from hot alcohol in colourless needles, m.p. 131-32° (Found: N, 4.15. $C_{22}H_{19}O_3N$ requires N, 4.06 per cent).

Methiodide of β -Hydroxyphenylethylamine (IV).—A mixture of β -hydroxyphenylethylamine (1 g.), methyl iodide (4 c.c.) in dry benzene deposited the methiodide after standing for 12 hours. It was collected, washed with dry ether and crystallised from hot alcohol in fine needles, m.p. 222°. (Found: N, 4.3; I, 42.0. $C_{11}H_8ONI$ requires N, 4.54; I, 41.3 per cent).

β -Hydroxyphenylethylamine did not condense with dimethyl cyanamide under varying conditions of experiment.

Piperonylidine- β -hydroxyphenylethylamine, m.p. 105-106° after crystallisation from alcohol, was prepared by condensing the base with piperonal in boiling alcohol in presence of caustic soda solution. (Found: N, 5.20. $C_{16}H_{15}O_4N$ requires N, 5.24 per cent).

β -Hydroxy- β -phenylethylmethylamine—The foregoing Schiff's base (3 g.) dissolved in dry benzene (60 c.c.) was treated with methyl iodide (5 c.c.) and left for 2 days and then refluxed for 1 hour. The methyl iodide addition product separated as a sticky solid. This was dissolved in hot water and treated with hydrochloric acid and warmed for an hour. After

cooling, the solution was extracted with ether to remove piperonal formed by hydrolysis and the aqueous portion made alkaline and the base extracted with ether. The ethereal solution furnished a solid which was directly converted into the picronolate as brilliant yellow needles, m.p. 196-98° after crystallisation from hot alcohol. (Found: C, 55.1; H, 5.2; N, 16.93. $C_{19}N_2O_8$ requires C, 54.9; H, 5.0; N, 16.87 per cent).

Cyanhydrin of Piperonal.—The following method gives a good yield of the cyanhydrin of piperonal. To a solution of piperonal (20 g.) in hot alcohol (20 c.c.) a solution of sodium hydrogen sulphite (30 g. in 50 c.c. of water) was added with shaking. The bisulphite compound was collected after cooling and washed with ether. The bisulphite compound suspended in water (ca 20 c.c.) was shaken with a solution of potassium cyanide (20 g.) in water (20 c.c.) in the cold. The resulting cyanhydrin was extracted with ether, yield 16-18 g.

β -3':4'-Methylenedioxyphenylethylamine.—Piperonal cyanhydrin (16 g.) in 50% alcohol (220 c.c.) was reduced with sodium amalgam (500 g. of 4%) and the product isolated essentially as described under β -hydroxy- β -phenylethylamine except that chloroform was used for the extraction of the free base. The base was converted into the carbonate (yield 3-4 g.) in chloroform solution, m.p. 116-19° (decomp.). The hydrochloride crystallises from hot alcohol, m.p. 182-83°. (Found: N, 6.38; Cl, 16.7. $C_9H_{12}O_3NCl$ requires N, 6.45; Cl, 16.3 per cent). The *picronolate* crystallises in fine yellow needles, m.p. 200° (decomp.). (Found: N, 15.47. $C_{19}H_{19}O_8N_5$ requires N, 15.75 per cent). The *oxalate* crystallises in plates, m.p. 197°. (Found: N, 4.78. $C_{11}H_{13}O_7N$ requires N, 5.1 per cent). The carbonate was benzoylated with benzoyl chloride and aqueous alkali. The mono-*N*-benzoyl derivative crystallises from hot alcohol in fine needles, m.p. 152-53°. (Found: N, 5.05. $C_{16}H_{15}O_4N$ requires N, 4.91 per cent). The *O-N*-dibenzoyl derivative is formed in pyridine solution and crystallises from alcohol in colourless needles, m.p. 141-42°. (Found: N, 4.5. $C_{23}H_{19}O_5N$ requires N, 4.1 per cent).

β -3':4'-Methylenedioxyphenylethyl trimethylammonium Iodide (structure analogous to IV).—The base described above (2 g.) was treated with methyl iodide (4 c.c.) in benzene. The methiodide crystallises from hot alcohol in needles, m.p. 229-30°. (Found: C, 40.8; H, 5.3; N, 4.46. $C_{12}H_{18}O_3NI$ requires C, 41.0; H, 5.1; N, 4.0 per cent).

Piperonylidine- β -hydroxy- β -3':4'-methylenedioxyphenylethylamine.—The Schiff's base was prepared in alcoholic solution in presence of alkali and had m.p. 155-56° after crystallisation from alcohol. (Found: N, 4.26. $C_{18}H_{19}O_5N$ requires N, 4.28 per cent).

The foregoing Schiff's base (2.7 g.), dissolved in dry benzene (100 c.c.), was refluxed with methyl iodide (5 c.c.) for 2 hours. On standing a semi-solid mass separated, which was dissolved in water and hydrolysed with hydrochloric acid. The acidic solution after being freed from piperonal by extraction with ether was basified and again extracted with ether. The oily base (β -hydroxy- β -3:4-methylenedioxyphenylethylmethylamine, III) obtained from ether was converted into picronolate, which crystallised in bright yellow needles, m.p. 203°. (Found: N, 14.81. $C_{20}H_{21}O_8N_5$ requires N, 15.2 per cent).

The Hydroiodide of the Base (II).—An alcoholic solution of β -hydroxyphenylethylamine (3 g. in 15 c.c.) was refluxed with methyl- ψ -thiourea hydroiodide (4 g.) on the steam-bath for 3 hours, when methyl sulphhydrate was copiously evolved. The reaction mixture was freed from alcohol in *vacuo* and the syrupy residue was stirred with ether when it solidified to a cake. It crystallises from ethyl acetate in large colourless prisms, m.p. 133°. The substance gave a positive Sakaguchi's test for a guanidine derivative, yield 5 g. (Found: N, 13.4; I, 40.8. $C_9H_{14}ON_3I$ requires N, 13.6; I, 41.4 per cent).